

Search Protocol for Policy Documents on Micronutrients

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Objective: To identify policy documents that relate to micronutrient (MN) intake, absorption, status, requirements¹, deficiency, availability (nutrient density), growth, development and health or disease.

Research Q1:

What are the primary factors contributing to inadequate or low micronutrient intakes and low or deficient status for one or more micronutrients in Europe, and how do these factors vary across different demographic groups and regions?

This research question aims to identify the main causes of inadequate or low micronutrient intakes and low or deficient status for one or more micronutrients within the European context. It explores how various factors such as dietary patterns, socioeconomic conditions, access to healthcare, health status, clinical condition, disease, and regional policies influence these low intakes and low or deficient status. Additionally, it considers the differences across demographic groups (e.g., age, sex, socioeconomic status, cultural and religious factors) and geographic regions (e.g., Northern vs. Southern Europe) to provide a comprehensive understanding of the issues.

Research Q2:

What strategies can be implemented to address inadequate or low micronutrient intakes and low or deficient status for one or more micronutrients in Europe, considering diverse dietary habits and socioeconomic conditions across the continent?

This research question aims to explore and identify actionable solutions to combat micronutrient deficiencies in Europe. It considers the effectiveness of various strategies, such as public health interventions, including nutritional guidelines, policy changes, educational programs, and improvements in food fortification and access to dietary supplements. The question also considers the diverse dietary habits and socioeconomic conditions not only across different European regions but also across communities and populations within the same geographical

¹ https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2017_09_DRVs_summary_report.pdf
https://www.espen.org/files/ESPEN-Guidelines/ESPEN_micronutrient_guideline.pdf

areas or between urban and rural areas, ensuring that proposed solutions are adaptable and relevant to various contexts within the continent.

Research Q3:

What are the key challenges to the successful implementation and effectiveness of strategies aimed at combating micronutrient deficiencies in Europe?

This research question seeks to uncover the obstacles that hinder the success of interventions designed to reduce micronutrient deficiencies across Europe. It focuses on identifying specific barriers such as political, cultural, educational/public awareness, economic, logistical, or food-related issues that may impact the implementation and efficacy of these strategies. Additionally, it examines behavioural factors that might influence dietary choices and adoption of nutritional interventions. The question also considers environmental and seasonal influences, which can affect the availability and potency of micronutrient-rich foods and the synthesis/accumulation of micronutrients in foods. Understanding these challenges is crucial for developing more effective and sustainable solutions to address micronutrient deficiencies in the region.

1. Databases and Resources:

1. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)
2. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) website
3. GAIN
4. Micronutrient Forum
5. Nutrition International
6. OpenGrey
7. Publications Office of the European Union
8. PubMed
9. World Bank
10. World Health Organization (WHO) website

2. Search Terms:

Consider:

- British and US spellings (anaemia versus anemia, i.e., OR)
- Singular (deficiency versus deficiencies, i.e., deficienc*)

General nutrients terms:

- Micronutrient
- Mineral
- Malnutrition
- Vitamin
- Hidden hunger
- Dietary
- Minimum Dietary diversity

Descriptive Terms:

- Absorption
- Adequacy
- Consumption
- Deficiency
- Excess
- Fortification
- Supplementation
- Inadequacy
- Insufficiency
- Intake
- Requirements
- Standards

Document Types:

- Guidelines
- Initiatives
- Policy
- Programmes
- Regulations
- Reports

Geographical Region:

- Europe

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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

3. Research Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria: Policy documents, guidelines, and reports that:

- Have been published between 1995 and 2024.
- Are written or translated in English.
- Focus on the Europe / European region.
- Are available on open access and subscription-based resources.
- Address micronutrient deficiencies in Europe.

Exclusion Criteria: Policy documents, guidelines, and reports that:

- Do not address the public health interventions, or programmes on micronutrient deficiencies
- Do not focus on European countries or regions within Europe
- Are Originated from the private sector, that pose potential conflicts of interest, Animal studies or in vitro research
- Are Not available in English or without an English translation.
- Are Older than 30 years
- Are Related to famine, starvation, etc.
- Are Focus on, dieting trends, feedstuffs, alternative medicines

4. Search Steps:

Step 1: Initial search

- Design a search phrase.
- Conduct initial searches on PubMed
- Review titles and abstracts to filter relevant documents using a screening tool (Rayyan).
- Collect and systematically organize references using a citation management software (Mendeley)

Step 2: Focused search on specific websites

- Use internal search engines to find documents related to micronutrient policies where the “advanced search” option is available.
- Look for policy sections, health guidelines, and relevant reports.
- If “advanced search” is not available, use a google query along with a scraping tool (i.e. ImportFromWeb) to automate the extraction of search results.

Step 3: remaining sources from subtask WP 9.2

- Conduct interviews with experts on micronutrients from academia and institutions involved in the Zero Hidden Hunger EU project.
- Sources gathered from these interviews will be included, if considered relevant, to the body of sources used for the analysis.

Step 4: Data Extraction

- Title of the document
- Author(s) or issuing organization
- Publication date
- Geographic focus
- Key micronutrient(s) covered
- Policy type (e.g., guideline, regulation, recommendation)
- Policy target
- Demographic:
 - o Age
 - o Gender
 - o Area
 - o Risk population
- Key findings and/or recommendations
 - o Health outcomes (general or micronutrients specific)
- Implementation status (if available)

Step 6: Data synthesis

- Compile a summary of the findings, categorizing by region and type of policy.
- Highlight major themes, inconsistencies, and gaps in current policies.
- Provide recommendations for future research or policy development.

Search Phrases used on PubMed:

(Micronutrient* OR Mineral* OR Vitamin* OR Hidden hunger OR Minimum Dietary diversity OR Dietary OR Malnutrition) AND (Absorption OR Adequa* OR Consumption OR Deficien* OR Excess OR Fortification OR Supplement* OR Inadequa* OR Insufficien* OR Intake OR Requirements OR Standards) AND (Guidelines OR Initiative* OR Polic* OR Program* OR Regulation* OR Report) AND (Europ*)

Filters applied: Government Publication, Guideline, Legislation, Practice Guideline, Technical Report, English
Publication Date = 1995 -2025

Simplified search Phrases used on Google:

(micronutrient OR micronutrients OR mineral OR minerals OR vitamin OR vitamins)
(deficiency OR deficiencies OR inadequacy OR inadequacies OR insufficiency OR insufficiencies OR consumption OR fortification OR supplementation OR intake OR requirements OR standard OR standards) (guideline OR guidelines OR policy OR policies OR program OR programs OR regulation OR regulations) (Europe)
site:**WEBSITE.ORG/INT/EU filetype:pdf**